

Application of ammonium metavanadate for the determination of some tubercular and adrenocortical steroid drugs

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Abstract : A simple method has been developed for the determination of tubercular and adrenocortical steroid drugs e.g. isoniazid, ethambutol hydrochloride, rifampicin, pyrazinamide, cycloserine, betamethasone sodium phosphate, dexamethasone sodium phosphate, hydrocortisone sodium succinate and prednisolone sodium succinate in pure form and in their pharmaceutical preparations by ammonium metavanadate reagent in acidic medium.

Keywords : Ammonium metavanadate, adrenocortical drugs.

Tubercular and adrenocortical steroid drugs possess great medicinal value and a number of methods are available for their estimation¹. In the present communication we report a simple method for the determination of these drugs, like isoniazid, ethambutol hydrochloride, rifampicin etc.

Results and discussion

The reaction conditions were established after studying the effect of variables such as reaction time, concentration and amount of reagent and sulphuric acid and reaction temperature. All the antitubercular drugs need 30 min and adrenocortical steroid drugs need 45 min to complete the reaction. The variation in the reaction time is due to difference in the structure of the compounds. The effect of concentration (0.01–0.5 N) of reagent (AMV) recommended that 0.3 N was suitable for accurate and concordant results. The presence of sulphuric acid was found to accelerate the reaction. The reactivity of the sample is very slow at ice cold temperature but increases with temperature (5–100 °C). Direct heating of the reaction mixture on flame or on sand bath was avoided because it gives inconsistent results. The stoichiometric ratio of the reagent with the sample has also been established for each compound. It varies with the structure of the compound. The present reagent works as a strong oxidizing agent and gives corresponding oxidized products consuming variable moles of the reagent. The determinations were done with varying sample sizes i.e. (1–10 mg) but for convenience results has been shown only with 3 mg sample size (Table 1). Recovery

Table 1. Determination of some antitubercular drugs in pure form and their pharmaceutical preparations with 0.3 N ammonium metavanadate reagent in acidic medium

Sl. no.	Drugs	Molecularity	Amount obtained by calculation ^a (mg)	SD (mg)	RSD (%)
Antitubercular drugs (3 mg in 3.0 ml, reaction time 30 min) :					
1.	Pyrazinamide (Pure)	6	2.9917	0.0039	0.1304
a.	P-zide (T) (Cadila Pharma)	6	2.9935	0.0046	0.1536
b.	Pyzina (T) (Lupin Labs)	6	2.9899	0.0042	0.1405
2.	Isoniazid (Pure)	4	2.9912	0.0045	0.1504
a.	Isokin (T) (Werner Lab)	4	2.9903	0.0038	0.1270
b.	Isonex (T) (Pfizer Ltd.)	4	2.9909	0.0052	0.1738
3.	Ethambutol hydrochloride (Pure)	8	2.9916	0.0039	0.1303
a.	Combital (T) (Lupin Labs)	8	2.9927	0.0036	0.1203
b.	Mycobital (Cap) (Cadila Pharma)	8	2.9910	0.0041	0.1370
4.	Rifampicin (Pure)	16	2.9915	0.0037	0.1237
a.	R-Cin (Cap) (Lupin Labs)	16	2.9920	0.0042	0.1404
b.	Zucocin (Cap) (Glaxo Ltd.)	16	2.9850	0.0041	0.1373

Note

Table-1 (contd.)					Table-1 (contd.)						
5.	Cycloserine (Pure)	6	2.9885	0.0042	0.1405	b.	Primacort (Inj) (Macleods Ltd.)	32	2.9790	0.0031	0.1040
a.	Cyclorine (Cap) (Lupin Labs)	6	2.9845	0.0039	0.1307	4.	Prednisolone sodium succinate (Pure)	32	2.9770	0.0034	0.1142
Adrenocortical steroid drugs (3 mg in 3.0 ml, reaction time 45 min) :											
1.	Betamethasone sodium phosphate (Pure)	30	2.9790	0.0031	0.1040	a.	Ne-Drol (Inj) (VHB Ltd.)	32	2.9820	0.0035	0.1174
a.	Betnesol (Inj) (Glaxo Ltd.)	30	2.9820	0.0035	0.1174	^a In each case five determinations were done. T = tablet, Cap = capsule, Inj = injection.					
b.	Salubet (Inj) (Lupin Labs)	30	2.9810	0.0034	0.1140	percentages were calculated by the following expression (Table 2).					
2.	Dexamethasone sodium phosphate (Pure)	30	2.9790	0.0035	0.1175	$\text{Recovery (\%)} = \frac{N\sum XY - \sum X\sum Y \times 100}{N\sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2}$					
a.	Dexona (Inj) (Cadila Ltd.)	30	2.9770	0.0029	0.0974	X = standard drug added, Y = amount of drug obtained, N = number of observation.					
b.	Stedex (Inj) (Ind Snwift)	30	2.9840	0.0035	0.1173	On the basis of molecularity and available literature a possible course of reaction may be suggested for each antitubercular and adrenocortical steroid compounds. Since, isolation of the final reaction products and their identification has not been possible, it may be proposed					
3.	Hydrocortisone sodium succinate (Pure)	32	2.9800	0.0031	0.1040						
a.	HSS (Inj) (Shree Ganesh Ltd.)	32	2.9840	0.0033	0.1106						

Table 2. Recovery studies of some antitubercular and adrenocortical steroids by standard drug addition method

Sl. no.	Sample of tubercular drugs	No. of observation	Aliquots taken (ml)	Amount of drug present (pure) (mg)	Amount of drug added (mg) X	Total amount of drug obtained (mg)	Amount of added drug obtained (mg) Y	XY	X ²	Recovery
1.	Pyrazinamide	3.0	1.0	1.0	3.0	3.9903	2.9903	8.9709	9	99.74
2.	Isoniazid	3.0	1.0	1.0	3.0	3.9921	2.9921	8.9763	9	99.69
3.	Ethambutol hydrochloride	3.0	3.0	45	3.0	3.9980	2.9980	8.9940	9	99.79
4.	Rifampicin	3.0	3.0	45	3.0	3.9941	2.9941	8.9823	9	99.74
5.	Cycloserine	3.0	3.0	45	3.0	3.9970	2.9970	8.9910	9	99.78
Adrenocortical steroids :										
1.	Betamethasone sodium phosphate	3.0	1.0	1.0	3.0	3.9860	2.9860	8.9580	9	99.66
2.	Dexamethasone sodium phosphate	3.0	1.0	1.0	3.0	3.9900	2.9900	8.9700	9	99.67
3.	Hydrocortisone sodium succinate	3.0	1.0	1.0	3.0	3.9900	2.9900	8.9700	9	99.53
4.	Prednisolone sodium succinate	3.0	1.0	1.0	3.0	3.9880	2.9880	8.9640	9	99.76

that the compounds get oxidized to suitable corresponding products.

Experimental

Ammonium metavanadate dissolved in 5 ml of conc. sulphuric acid in a 100 ml volumetric flask and made up to the mark with distilled water. The solution was standardized iodometrically.

Accurately weighed (100 mg) sample of pure compounds like isoniazid, ethambutol hydrochloride, rifampicin, pyrazinamide, cycloserine, betamethasone sodium phosphate, dexamethasone sodium phosphate, hydrocortisone sodium succinate and prednisolone sodium succinate were dissolved in distilled water in a 100 ml volumetric flask.

In the case of tablets twenty tablets of a particular sample were crushed to a fine powder and 100 mg of the

sample was taken in a 100 ml volumetric flask and dissolved accordingly. For injection and capsules amount equivalent to 100 mg of the pure sample were taken and dissolved in distilled water, in a 100 ml volumetric flask. An aliquot containing 1–5 mg of sample was taken in a 100 ml stoppered flask followed by the addition of 5 ml, 0.3 N ammonium metavanadate and titrated iodometrically.

References

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